

Synthesis, characterization, thermal, electrical and antibacterial studies of complexes of bivalent metal ions

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Metal complexes of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with 2-amino-4-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)thiazole (AHMPTZ) have been synthesized. Isolated complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic measurements, IR and electronic spectral data and thermogravimetry. The solid state conductivity of ligand and its complexes have been measured in their compressed pellet form in the temperature range 40–200°C. The antimicrobial activity of ligand and its complexes has been screened *in vitro* against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Numerous applications of thiazole derivatives^{1,2} and their increased biological activity on coordination with suitable metal ions due to heterocyclic ring containing sulphur, nitrogen and or oxygen has been reported³. In view of the above, 2-amino-4-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-thiazole (AHMPTZ) and its complexes of bivalent metal ions have been prepared and characterized by their analytical, magnetic, IR, reflectance spectral data and thermal analysis. The ligand and its complexes have also been studied for their antimicrobial and electrical properties.

Results and discussion

Elemental analyses data (Table 1) and determined molecular weight suggest 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry and monomeric nature (ML_2) of the complexes. All the complexes are found to be insoluble in water and common organic solvents, but sparingly soluble in DMF and DMSO. The low conductance values (8-21 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in DMF ($10^{-3} M$) showed their non-electrolytic nature. The 1H NMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of ligand is as follows : δ 2.3 (2H, s, CH_3), 6.8 (1H, s, CH), 6.9–7.1 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.8 (2H, s, NH_2)⁴.

The IR spectrum of ligand shows a medium intensity band at 2925 cm^{-1} due to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the thiazole forming a stable six-membered ring⁵. Absence of this band in complexes indicates the destruction of the intramolecular-hydrogen bonding followed by complexation of phenolic oxygen after proton replacement. This is further supported by the shift of $\nu(C-O)$ stretch from

1260 to 1276–1296 cm^{-1} in the complexes and appearance of a new low intensity bands at 520–573 cm^{-1} due M–O vibrations. The bands at 3338 and 691 cm^{-1} due NH and C–S–C modes, respectively, are not affected in the complexes indicating their non participation in coordination. The $\nu(C=N)$ stretch shifts to lower frequency in the complexes by 10–17 cm^{-1} , suggesting involvement of nitrogen in coordination⁶. This is further supported by the appearance of a new low intensity bands at 450–475 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes due to the $\nu(M-N)$ stretch. In addition, Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes exhibit characteristic bands due to coordination of water molecules⁷ at ~ 3400 , 1460–1490 and 820–830 cm^{-1} .

The diffuse reflectance spectrum of Mn^{II} complex shows three weak bands at 14430, 16600 and 22271 cm^{-1} . These band may be assigned due to $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}$ (4G), $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$ (4F) and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g$, $^4A_{1g}$ (4F), transitions respectively, in an octahedral environment⁸. The magnetic moment value of 5.96 B.M. is also consistent with high-spin octahedral structure. The reflectance spectrum of the iron(II) complex also exhibits three absorption bands at 11764, 15338 and 19607 cm^{-1} normally expected for an octahedral structure. The first band is assigned due to the $^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow ^5E_g$ transition, while other two bands are due to charge transfer in origin for high spin octahedral complex⁹. The magnetic moment, 5.94 B.M. also supplements high spin octahedral geometry. The three bands in the cobalt complex at 9803, 15630 and 22988 cm^{-1} corresponds to transitions $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$, $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow$

Table 1. The analytical, physical and conductivity data of complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Mol. wt. (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.) (%)					μ_{eff} B.M.	Solid state conductivity ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	Activation energy, E_a (eV)
				C	H	N	S	M			
1.	AHMPTZ	Yellow	204.5 (206)	56.91 (57.59)	4.18 (4.80)	12.96 (13.46)	19.12 (19.38)	-	-	8.92×10^{-6} 4.64×10^{-5}	0.250
2.	[Mn(AHMPTZ) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	499.00 (500.94)	46.32 (47.90)	3.61 (3.99)	10.89 (11.17)	11.87 (12.77)	10.80 (10.96)	5.69	1.08×10^{-8} 2.21×10^{-6}	0.449
3.	[Fe(AHMPTZ) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish red	498.20 (501.85)	46.80 (47.82)	3.90 (3.98)	10.55 (11.15)	11.85 (12.75)	10.83 (11.12)	5.94	1.81×10^{-8} 1.50×10^{-6}	0.682
4.	[Co(AHMPTZ) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown red	502.50 (506.93)	47.5 (47.34)	3.71 (3.94)	10.78 (11.04)	11.2 (12.62)	11.52 (11.62)	5.18	2.10×10^{-8} 1.81×10^{-5}	0.254
5.	[Ni(AHMPTZ) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂]	Light yellow	500.00 (506.70)	46.22 (47.36)	3.41 (3.94)	10.32 (11.05)	11.92 (12.63)	10.77 (11.58)	3.20	1.45×10^{-8} 1.76×10^{-5}	0.273
6.	[Cu(AHMPTZ) ₂]	Green	478.45 (477.55)	47.82 (50.25)	4.20 (4.18)	10.93 (11.72)	12.50 (13.40)	12.71 (13.30)	1.98	1.66×10^{-8} 2.54×10^{-8}	0.245
7.	[Zn(AHMPTZ) ₂]	Light brown	471.00 (475.38)	48.97 (50.48)	4.00 (4.20)	10.96 (11.78)	12.71 (13.46)	12.20 (13.75)	Dia.	5.11×10^{-6} 2.35×10^{-5}	0.182
8.	[Cd(AHMPTZ) ₂]	Shell white	509.52 (522.4)	48.33 (49.94)	3.20 (3.82)	10.50 (10.70)	11.57 (12.25)	21.00 (21.43)	Dia.	5.32×10^{-8} 1.16×10^{-5}	0.190

${}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, in an octahedral geometry¹⁰. The magnetic moment of Co^{II} complex is 5.18 B.M. which is in good agreement with high-spin octahedral geometry. This value is higher than the spin-only value (3.87 B.M.) and may be ascribed to substantial orbital contribution to the moment¹¹. The Ni^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 11834, 16583 and 23255 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively and the position of bands is indicative of an octahedral structure¹². The observed magnetic moment of the complex is 3.20 B.M., which is within the expected range for Ni^{II} ion in an octahedral environment. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex shows three bands at 15556, 19230 and 23255 cm^{-1} , the first two bands may be due to the *d-d* transitions while third one may be assigned to charge transfer or intra-ligand transition suggesting the square-planar stereochemistry¹³. The room temperature magnetic moment value of 1.98 B.M. also supports the square planar geometry. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected for d^{10} system.

Thermal behaviour of all these complexes are nearly similar. Hence, only [Co(AHMPTZ)₂·2H₂O] and [Cu(AHMPTZ)₂] are discussed in detail. The anhydrous Cu^{II} complex is stable upto 200°C and then the organic part partially starts decomposing in two steps as shown in

equation :

The Co^{II} complex exhibits a weight loss of 8.10% in the temperature range 150–200°C against the theoretical value of 8.91%, and this corresponds to the loss of two coordinated water molecules. Thereafter, the decomposition of side chain of the ligand occurs which is followed by the decomposition of actually coordinated chromophore residue until the formation of Co₃O₄ as the end product at ca. 540°C.

The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of the ligand and its complexes in their compressed pellet of the powdered samples prepared at a load 6 Kilo Newton pressure has been measured in the temperature

range 313–473 K. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relation¹⁴ $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/KT)$, where symbols have usual meaning. The plot σ vs $1/T$ for all the compounds are found to be linear over a studied temperature range, indicating their semiconducting behaviour¹⁴. The room temperature electrical conductivity lies in the range 1.08 – $5.32 \times 10^{-8} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ also suggest their semiconducting behaviour. The activation energy of electrical conduction of chelates has been found to be decreased in the order : $\text{Fe} > \text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{AHMPTZ} > \text{Cu} > \text{Cd} > \text{Zn}$ which is in partial agreement with the reported results.

The antimicrobial activity of the ligand and its complexes were assessed against gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus* and *Bacillus*) and gram negative bacteria (*E. coli* and *Klebsiella*) at a concentration range of 30–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ by using agar diffusion method¹⁵. The DMSO was used as a control. A comparative study of the ligand and its complexes revealed that all the metal complexes exhibited antimicrobial activities (zone of inhibition 8–25 mm). In general metal complexes are more active than the ligand (zone of inhibition ~ 8 mm). The increased activities of the complexes as compared to the free ligand could also be understood in terms of chelation theory and overtone's concept. Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are more active as compared to their Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes for all bacterial species. The antimicrobial activity of the metal chelates was found to be in the orders : $\text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of AnalaR grade. 2-Amino-4-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)thiazole was prepared by the known method¹⁶. Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, ferrous ammonium sulphate hexahydrate, cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate, zinc(II) acetate dihydrate, copper(II) acetate monohydrate, cadmium(II) acetate tetrahydrate, DMF-DMSO, thiourea, *p*-cresol, AlCl_3 and acetic anhydride (S.D.'s fine) were used for synthesis.

Synthesis of cobalt(II) complex :

Methanolic solution of cobalt acetate (0.01 mol) was added dropwise to the ligand (0.02 mol) solution in DMF with constant stirring. The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding 2 ml, 2 M NaOAc. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h on an oil bath and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting reaction product was filtered, washed successively with small quantities of hot

water, methanol, DMF and finally with ether and then dried *in vacuo*. Other metal complexes were also synthesised using similar procedure.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 analyzer. IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer RX1 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectrum of the ligand was recorded in DMSO- d_6 at SAIF, Chandigarh. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded at SAIF, Chennai in the range 400–1200 nm on Varian Cary-5 spectrophotometer. The metal content of each complex was determined by independent gravimetric and volumetric methods. The magnetic measurements were made by Gouy method. The thermograms were recorded at USIC, Shivaji University, Kolhapur. The solid state conductivity was measured in their compressed pellet form prepared from powdered samples by conventional two probe method. Molar conductance was measured on a Systronic (Model 303) conductivity bridge in dry dimethylformamide. Molecular weights were determined by the Rast camphor method. The antimicrobial activity was studied by disc diffusion method¹⁵.

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